

SUG'ORILADIGAN HUDUDLARDA YER OSTI SUVLARI HARAKATINI MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada yer osti suvlarining harakati va sathini prognoz qilishga qaratilgan matematik modelning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari adabiyotlar asosida yoritilgan. Ushbu model sug'orish tizimlarini samarali boshqarish va suv resurslarini tejash imkoniyatini beradi. Model infiltratsiya jarayonlarini qisqa muddatli yog'ingarchiliklar va sug'orish suvlari orqali infiltratsion to'yinishni alohida ko'rib chiqadi, shuningdek, filtrlash koeffitsienti dinamik ravishda o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: yer osti suvlari sathi, koeffitsient filtratsiya, sug'orish suvi.

Abstract. This article explores the theoretical and practical aspects of a mathematical model for predicting the movement and level of groundwater based on reviewed literature. Applying this model allows for efficient management of irrigation systems and conservation of water resources. The model investigates infiltration processes by distinguishing between short-term precipitation-based infiltration saturation and saturation through irrigation water, with a dynamic approach to filtration coefficient analysis.

Keywords: groundwater level, filtration coefficient, irrigation water.

Kirish

Sug'orish tizimlari takroriy ekin ekiladigan hududlarda suv resurslarini samarali boshqarish uchun muhim hisoblanadi. Biroq, sug'orish natijasida yer osti suvlari harakati va sathining o'zgarishi murakkab gidrologik jarayonlarni yuzaga keltiradi. Ushbu jarayonlar tuproqning fizik xususiyatlari, suv oqimi va tarqalishi, hamda yer usti va osti sharoitlariga bog'liqdir. Shuning uchun yer osti suvlarining harakati va sathini aniq prognoz qilish sug'orish tizimlarini samarali boshqarish, suvni tejash va ekologik muammolarni oldini olish uchun zarurdir. N. Ravshanov, S. Daliyev, Z. Abdullayev va S.A. Zagrebina kabi olimlarning tadqiqotlarida yer osti suvlarining darajasi va tuz konsentratsiyasining o'zgarishini kuzatish va prognoz qilish, shuningdek, gidrotexnik inshootlarni loyihalashda suv toshqini, sho'rlanish va botqoqlanish jarayonlarini inobatga olish uchun matematik model ishlab chiqilgan. Ushbu mavzudagi tadqiqotlarning sifat tahlili keltirilgan. Jarayon chiziqli bo'lmagan differensial tenglama orqali ifodalanganligi sababli uni yechish uchun chekli farqlar usuliga asoslangan raqamli algoritm ishlab chiqilgan. Tuz migratsiyasini geofiltrlash jarayonlarining matematik modellari takomillashtirilib, hisoblash algoritmlari yaratilgan. Ikki qatlamli qatlamlarda faol g'ovaklik va oqim tezligini hisobga olgan holda yer osti suvlari darajasini o'zgartirish uchun raqamli algoritm ishlab chiqilgan [1-3].

I. Xabibullayev, B. T. Murodullayev va D. O. Haqnazarova takroriy ekin ekiladigan hududlarda yer usti suvlari bilan o'zaro aloqada bo'lgan yer osti suvlarining filtratsiya jarayonini sonli modelini yaratish va uni yechish masalasini ko'rib chiqdi. Maqolaning yechimini keltirishdan oldin, matematik va sonli modellashtirishga oid ilmiy maqolalar batafsil o'rganilib, tahlil qilingan. O'rganilayotgan suv qatlamida yer osti va suv darajasiga oid ko'rsatkichlar qiymatlari pastki gorizonttal suv o'tkazmaydigan qatlamga nisbatan olingan. Bunda suvli qatlamlarda yer osti suvlarining harakati matematik model sifatida parabolik turdagi hususiy

hosilali chiziqli bo‘lmagan differensial tenglama orqali tasvirlangan. O‘tkazilgan hisoblash tajribalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki, yer osti suv darajasiga filtrlash jarayonida sug‘oriladigan suvlar sezilarli ta’sir ko‘rsatadigan asosiy omil sifatida qaralgan [4-5]. J. Bear, A. Verruijt va T. P. Clement tadqiqotlarida yer osti suvlarining oqimi va ifloslanishi modellashtirilgan bo‘lib, yer osti suvlarining oqim modellari va ifloslanish transporti haqida fundamental bilimlar taqdim etilgan[6-7]. SEAWET va MODFLOW-2005 dasturiy ta’minoti uch o‘lchovli o‘zgaruvchan zichlikli yer osti suvlarining oqimini simulyatsiya qilish uchun ishlab chiqilgan. W. Guo va C. D. Langevin tadqiqotlarida dasturiy ta’minotning qo‘llanilishi va parametrizatsiyasi haqida tushunchalar berilgan[8, 9, 15]. G. M. Hornberger, L. F. Konikow, T. E. Reilly va E. W. Boyelarning tadqiqotlarida daryo oqimlarini generatsiya qilish jarayonidagi so‘nggi yutuqlar taqdim etilgan, shuningdek, daryo va yer osti suvlarining o‘zaro ta’siri haqida tushunchalar berilgan[10-11]. Yuqoridagi adabiyotlar sug‘orish tizimlari, yer osti suvlarining harakati va sathini bashoratlash bo‘yicha fundamental bilimlarni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Mavjud ishlarni tahlil qilish orqali yer osti suvlarining sathi va harakatini modellashtirish jarayonida har bir uchastka uchun individual parametrlar va ularga beriladigan resurslarni to‘g‘ri yo‘naltirish muhim va murakkab vazifa hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, sug‘oriladigan yer maydonlarida muhitning aksariyat hollarda bir jinsli bo‘lmasligi va ularga resurslarni teng taqsimlash muhitning suv bilan to‘yinishini ta’minlay olmasligini ko‘rdik. Sug‘oriladigan yer maydonlarida yetarli suv sathini ta’minlash, ortiqcha sathni tashqi omillar orqali muvozanatlash va yetarli bo‘lmagan sathga ega maydonlarni muntazam to‘ldirib borish nafaqat hosildorlikni, balki ekologik muammolarni bartaraf etishni ham anglatadi.

Masalaning qo‘yilishi: Takroriy ekin ekiladigan hududlardagi yer osti suvlarining harakatini tavsiflovchi matematik model takomillashtirilgan. Suvli qatlamdagi yer osti suv sathi pastki gorizonttal suv o‘tkazmaydigan qatlamga nisbatan olinib, bu harakat parabolik turdagi xususiy hosilali chiziqli bo‘lmagan differensial tenglama bilan ifodalanadi va u quyidagi ko‘rinishga ega bo‘ladi:

$$\mu \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \right) + W \quad (1)$$

va uning boshlang‘ich hamda chegaraviy shartlari quydagicha bo‘ladi:

$$h(x, y, 0) = h_0(x, y); \quad (2)$$

$$kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} = -\lambda(h - h_0), \quad kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=L} = \lambda(h - h_0), \quad (3)$$

$$kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \Big|_{y=0} = -\lambda(h - h_0), \quad kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \Big|_{y=L} = \lambda(h - h_0), \quad (4)$$

bu yerda h_0 -sizot suv sathining boshlang‘ich qiymati; λ -hisob chegarasi orqali massa almashinuv koeffitsiyenti; t_0 -boshlang‘ich vaqt; μ -suvli qatlamning suv berish qobiliyati (o‘lchovsiz qiymat); $h = h(x, y, t)$ -yer osti suvlarining suv o‘tkazmaydigan qatlamdan yer sirtigacha bo‘lgan darajasi qiymati; x, y -tekislik koordinatalari; t -vaqt, sutka; $k = k(x, y, t)$ -filtratsiya koeffitsienti va u quydagicha ifodalangan:

$$k(x, y, t) = k_0(x, y) \frac{h(x, y, t) + h_0(x, y)}{2h(x, y, t)}$$

bu yerda k_0 - filtratsiya koeffitsientining dastlabki qiymati; h_0 - dastlabki yer osti suvlari sathi.

W - ozod hadlarning algebraik yig'indisi va uning ifodalanishi:

$$W = \delta_{in}\eta_{in}Q_{in} - \delta_b\eta_bQ_b - \delta_d\eta_dQ_d + \delta_r\eta_rQ_r - \delta_z\eta_zQ_z + \delta_s\eta_sQ_s$$

bu yerda δ - derakt delta funktsiyasi; η - modelni o'lchovli ko'rinishga o'tkazish koeffitsiyenti (tengliklarning massa almashinuvi koeffitsiyenti)

$$\delta = \begin{cases} x = x_0, y = y_0, & 1 \\ x \neq x_0, y \neq y_0, & 0 \end{cases}$$

Q_d - yer ostidan olinadigan suv miqdori; Q_b - sathdan bug'lanish; Q_{in} - yer osti suvlarining atmosfera yog'inlari bilan infiltratsion to'yinishi; Q_r - kanallardan yer ostiga suv shimilishi; Q_z - yer ostidan suv chiqishi (zavurlarga); Q_s - sug'oriladigan davrda beriladigan suv miqdori. Q_s va Q_{in} modelda quyidagicha e'tiborga olinadi:

$$Q_{in} = \begin{cases} t \in T_{in}, & Q_y \\ t \notin T_{in}, & 0 \end{cases} \quad Q_s = \begin{cases} t \in T_{sug'}, & Q_{sug} \\ t \notin T_{sug'}, & 0 \end{cases}$$

(4)

bu yerda: Q_y - yog'in qiymati; Q_{sug} - sug'orish suvi qiymati.

Quyilgan masalani yechish uchun ushbu

$$h^* = \frac{h}{h_0}, k^* = \frac{k}{k_0}, x^* = \frac{x}{L}, y^* = \frac{y}{L}, \tau = \frac{k_0 h_0}{\mu L^2} t,$$

$$\eta_{in} = \frac{2L^2}{k_0 h_0^2}, \eta_b = \frac{2L^2}{k_0 h_0^2}, \eta_d = \frac{2L}{k_0 h_0^2}, \eta_r = \frac{2L}{k_0 h_0^2}, \eta_z = \frac{2L}{k_0 h_0^2}, \eta_s = \frac{L^2}{k_0 h_0^2}.$$

o'lchovsiz kattaliklarni kiritamiz.

U holda (1) – (4) yer osti sizot suv sathi o'zgarish jarayoni matematik modeli va mos chegaraviy shartlari quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

$$\frac{1}{h} \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k^* \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k^* \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial y} \right) + 2W^* \quad (5)$$

$$\left. \frac{k_0 h_0}{L} k^* h^* \frac{\partial h^*}{\partial x^*} \right|_{x^*=0} = -\lambda(h_0 h^* - h_0^2), \quad \left. \frac{k_0 h_0}{L} k^* h^* \frac{\partial h^*}{\partial x^*} \right|_{x^*=1} = \lambda(h_0 h^* - h_0^2), \quad (6)$$

$$\left. \frac{k_0 h_0}{L} k^* h^* \frac{\partial h^*}{\partial y^*} \right|_{y^*=0} = -\lambda(h_0 h^* - h_0^2), \quad \left. \frac{k_0 h_0}{L} k^* h^* \frac{\partial h^*}{\partial y^*} \right|_{y^*=1} = \lambda(h_0 h^* - h_0^2), \quad (7)$$

Soddalashtirish maqsadida (5) tenglamani va (6) – (7) chegaraviy shartlardagi «*» belgisini tushirib qoldiramiz, tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozamiz:

$$\frac{1}{h} \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial y} \right) + 2W \quad (8)$$

boshlang'ich vaqt $\tau = \tau_0$ bo'lsin. U holda boshlang'ich shart va chegaraviy shartlar:

$$h|_{\tau=\tau_0} = h_0, \quad (9)$$

$$\left. \frac{k_0 h_0^2}{L} k h \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} = -\lambda(h_0 h - h_0^2), \quad \left. \frac{k_0 h_0^2}{L} k h \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \right|_{x=1} = \lambda(h_0 h - h_0^2), \quad (10)$$

$$\left. \frac{k_0 h_0^2}{L} kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = -\lambda(h_0 h - h_0^2), \quad \left. \frac{k_0 h_0^2}{L} kh \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \right|_{y=1} = \lambda(h_0 h - h_0^2), \quad (11)$$

(1)-(8) masalalar chiziqli bo‘lmagan differensial tenglamalar sistemalari bilan ifodalanganligi sababli ularni analitik usulda yechish murakkab bo‘ladi. Shu bois ko‘rilayotgan masalalarning yechimlarini topish uchun sonli usullardan foydalanamiz.

(1)-(4) masalalarni sonli yechish uchun chekli ayirmalar usulini qo‘llaymiz. Buning uchun $D = \{0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 \leq y \leq 1, 0 \leq t \leq N, \}$ sohaga to‘r kiratamiz, bu yerda izlanayotgan jarayon oralig‘idagi N maksimal vaqt, D sohaning $[0,1]$ va $[0,1]$ intervali, Δx , Δy qadamlar, $[0, N]$ ni $\Delta \tau$ qadam bilan bo‘lib chiqamiz va quyidagi to‘rga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\omega_{\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta \tau} = \{x = i\Delta x; i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, I; \quad y = j\Delta y; j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, J; \quad t_n = n\Delta \tau; n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N\},$$

$n + \frac{1}{2}$ qatlamda (8) tenglama hamda (10) – (11) chegaraviy shartlarni $\omega_{\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta \tau}$ to‘rda oshkormas sxemani qo‘llab approksimatsiya qilib quyidagi chekli ayirmali tenglamalarga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\tilde{h}_{i,j}} \frac{(h^2)_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - (h^2)_{i,j}^n}{0.5\Delta \tau} &= \frac{k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} (h^2)_{i-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} - \frac{(k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}})(h^2)_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} (h^2)_{i+1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} + \\ &+ \frac{k_{i,j-0.5}^n (h^2)_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y^2} - \frac{(k_{i,j-0.5}^n + k_{i,j+0.5}^n)(h^2)_{i,j}^n}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{k_{i,j+0.5}^n (h^2)_{i,j+1}^n}{\Delta y^2} + 2W_{i,j}^n. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

(12) tenglamani sath funksiyasining kvadratiga nisbatan $h^2 \approx 2\tilde{h}h - \tilde{h}^2$ kabi yozamiz. o‘xshash hadlarni ixchamlaganimizdan keyin chekli-ayirmani algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi ko‘rinishida ifodalaymiz:

$$a_{i,j} h_{i-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - b_{i,j} h_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + c_{i,j} h_{i+1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = -d_{i,j}, \quad (13)$$

bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} a_{i,j} &= \frac{2k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2}, \quad b_{i,j} = \frac{2 \left(k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \tilde{h}_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} - \frac{4}{\Delta \tau}, \quad c_{i,j} = \frac{2k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i+1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2}, \\ d_{i,j} &= \left(\frac{4}{\Delta \tau} - \frac{2(k_{i,j-0.5}^n + k_{i,j+0.5}^n) \tilde{h}_{i,j}^n}{\Delta y^2} \right) h_{i,j}^n + \frac{2k_{i,j-0.5}^n \tilde{h}_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y^2} h_{i,j-1}^n + \\ &+ \frac{2k_{i,j+0.5}^n \tilde{h}_{i,j+1}^n}{\Delta y^2} h_{i,j+1}^n - \frac{k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\left(k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \tilde{h}_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} - \frac{k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i+1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}}{\Delta x^2} - \\ &- \frac{k_{i,j-0.5}^n \tilde{h}_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{\left(k_{i,j-0.5}^n + k_{i,j+0.5}^n \right) \tilde{h}_{i,j}^n}{\Delta y^2} - \frac{k_{i,j+0.5}^n \tilde{h}_{i,j+1}^n}{\Delta y^2} + 2W_{i,j}^n. \end{aligned}$$

Oy yo‘nalishida (13) tenglamani $\omega_{\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta \tau}$ to‘rda oshkormas sxemani qo‘llab approksimatsiya qilamiz, sath funksiyasining kvadratiga nisbatan ifodadan foydalanib va uni uch diagonalli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi ko‘rinishida quyidagicha ifodalaymiz:

$$\bar{a}_{i,j} h_{i,j-1}^{n+1} - \bar{b}_{i,j} h_{i,j}^{n+1} + \bar{c}_{i,j} h_{i,j+1}^{n+1} = -\bar{d}_{i,j}, \quad (14)$$

bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a}_{i,j} &= \frac{2k_{i,j-0.5}^{n+1} \tilde{h}_{i,j-1}}{\Delta y^2}, \quad \bar{b}_{i,j} = \frac{2(k_{i,j-0.5}^{n+1} + k_{i,j+0.5}^{n+1}) \tilde{h}_{i,j}}{\Delta y^2} - \frac{4}{\Delta \tau}, \quad \bar{c}_{i,j} = \frac{2k_{i,j+0.5}^{n+1} \tilde{h}_{i,j+1}}{\Delta y^2}, \\ \bar{d}_{i,j} &= \left(\frac{4}{\Delta \tau} - \frac{2 \left(k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \tilde{h}_{i,j}}{\Delta x^2} \right) h_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i-1,j}}{\Delta x^2} h_{i-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \\ &+ \frac{2k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i+1,j}}{\Delta x^2} h_{i+1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i-1,j}^2}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\left(k_{i-0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \tilde{h}_{i,j}^2}{\Delta x^2} - \frac{k_{i+0.5,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{h}_{i+1,j}^2}{\Delta x^2} - \\ &- \frac{k_{i,j-0.5}^{n+1} \tilde{h}_{i,j-1}^2}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{\left(k_{i,j-0.5}^{n+1} + k_{i,j+0.5}^{n+1} \right) \tilde{h}_{i,j}^2}{\Delta y^2} - \frac{k_{i,j+0.5}^{n+1} \tilde{h}_{i,j+1}^2}{\Delta y^2} + 2W_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned}$$

(13) va (14) tenglamalar progonka metodidan foydalanib hisoblaymiz: Ox yo‘nalishida:

$$h_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \alpha_{i+1,j} h_{i+1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \beta_{i+1,j}, \quad (15)$$

Oy yo‘nalishida:

$$h_{i,j}^{n+1} = \bar{\alpha}_{i,j+1} h_{i,j+1}^{n+1} + \bar{\beta}_{i,j+1}, \quad (16)$$

kabi rekurrent formulalardan foydalanib (15) va (16) larda $\alpha_{i,j}, \beta_{i,j}, \bar{\alpha}_{i,j}, \bar{\beta}_{i,j}$ larni topish uchun i ni $i-1$ ga, j ni $j-1$ ga almashtiramiz:

$$h_{i-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \alpha_{i,j} h_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \beta_{i,j}, \quad h_{i,j-1}^{n+1} = \bar{\alpha}_{i,j} h_{i,j}^{n+1} + \bar{\beta}_{i,j}$$

bu yerda $\alpha_{i,j}, \beta_{i,j}, \bar{\alpha}_{i,j}, \bar{\beta}_{i,j}$ lar progonka koeffitsiyentlari, hisob kitoblardan so‘ng Ox, Oy yo‘nalishlari uchun progonka koeffitsiyentlarini topish uchun quyidagi rekurentlardan foydalanamiz:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{c_{i-1,j}}{b_{i-1,j} - a_{i-1,j} \alpha_{i-1,j}}, \quad \beta_i = \frac{d_{i-1,j} + a_{i-1,j} \beta_{i-1,j}}{b_{i-1,j} - a_{i-1,j} \alpha_{i-1,j}}, \quad (17)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_j = \frac{\bar{c}_{i,j-1}}{b_{i,j-1} - \bar{a}_{i,j-1} \bar{\alpha}_{i,j-1}}, \quad \bar{\beta}_j = \frac{\bar{d}_{i,j-1} + \bar{a}_{i,j-1} \bar{\beta}_{i,j-1}}{b_{i,j-1} - \bar{a}_{i,j-1} \bar{\alpha}_{i,j-1}}, \quad (18)$$

chegaraviy shartlarni oshkormas sxemani qo‘llab approksimatsiya qilamiz:

$$\text{Ox yo‘nalishi bo‘ylab: } \frac{k_0 h_0^2}{2L} k_{1,j} \frac{2h_{1,j} h_{1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - h_{1,j}^2 - 2h_{0,j} h_{0,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + h_{0,j}^2}{\Delta x} = -\lambda (h_0 h_{1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - h_0^2) \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{k_0 h_0^2}{2L} k_{I,j} \frac{2h_{I,j} h_{i,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - h_{I,j}^2 - 2h_{I-1,j} h_{I-1,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + h_{I-1,j}^2}{\Delta x} = \lambda(h_0 h_{I,j}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - h_0^2) \quad (20)$$

Oy yo‘nalishi bo‘ylab: $\frac{k_0 h_0^2}{2L} k_{i,1} \frac{2h_{i,1} h_{i,1}^{n+1} - h_{i,1}^2 - 2h_{i,0} h_{i,0}^{n+1} + h_{i,0}^2}{\Delta y} = -\lambda(h_0 h_{i,1}^{n+1} - h_0^2) \quad (21)$

$$\frac{k_0 h_0^2}{2L} k_{i,J} \frac{2h_{i,J} h_{i,J}^{n+1} - h_{i,J}^2 - 2h_{i,J-1} h_{i,J-1}^{n+1} + h_{i,J-1}^2}{\Delta y} = \lambda(h_0 h_{i,J}^{n+1} - h_0^2) \quad (22)$$

Yuqorida ta’kidlanganidek, muammo chiziqli bo‘lmagan qisman differensial tenglamalar yordamida tasvirlangan, uni iteratsion usul yordamida yechish mumkin. Takrorlanuvchi jarayonning yaqinlashuv shartlari quyidagilardan iborat:

$$\left| (h_{i,j})^{(s+1)} - (h_{i,j})^{(s)} \right| \leq \varepsilon.$$

bu yerda s – iteratsiyalar soni, ε – iteratsion jarayonning aniqligi (0.01).

Natijalar: Takroriy ekin ekiladigan hududlarning yer osti suvlarini harakatining takomillashtirilgan matematik modelda sonli tajriba natijalari keltirilgan:

1-rasm. Sug‘orilgan hududda quduq va zahkash qo‘llash holati hamda natijalari

2-rasm. Hududda kanal, quduq va zahkash qo‘llash holati hamda natijalari

Model va dasturiy majmualar yordamida hisoblash tajribalarni o‘tkazish hamda natijalarni tahlil qilish keltirilgan. Tahlil natijalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki:

3-rasm. Sath ko‘rsatkichlarini taqqoslash

Soha mutahassislari bizga taqdim etgan ma'lumotlarni ko'radigan bo'lsak, maydon sug'orilgandan keyin 72 soat kuzatish natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, dastlabki suv sathi 4.2 m edi. 5.75 soatdan keyin sug'orish suvi sathga yetib kelishni boshladi va eksponensial ko'zgara boshlagan. Natijada yer osti suv sathi 72 soatda 4.5 m ga erishgan. Takomillashtirilgan model natijalariga qaraydigan bo'lsak, dasturiy majmuadan olingan natijalar, dastlabki 4.2 m sath to'g'ridan-to'g'ri eksponensial holatda o'zgara boshladi va 72 soat davomida 4.4 m holatgacha ko'tarildi.

Yer osti suvlarining harakati va sathini bashoratlash uchun matematik model ishlab chiqildi. Taklif etilgan model yer usti va osti sharoitlariga bog'liq ravishda yer osti suvlarining harakat tezliklari va g'ovak muhitdagi suv konsentratsiyasini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Bu, o'z navbatida, yer osti suvlarining harakati va sathini aniq prognoz qilishni, sug'orish tizimlarini samarali boshqarishni, suv resurslarini tejashni va yer osti suvlari ifloslanishining oldini olishni, shuningdek, ekologik muammolarni hal qilish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa. Takroriy ekin ekiladigan hududlarda yer osti suvlarining filtratsiya jarayonlarini sonli modellashtirish xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar asosida amalga oshirildi. Tuzilgan model uchun chekli farqlar, progonka va iteratsiya usullari orqali sonli yechimlar ishlab chiqildi.

1. Tuzilgan sonli model va uni yechish uchun ishlab chiqilgan usullar quyidagi xulosalarni beradi:

2. Takroriy ekin ekiladigan va sug'oriladigan yerlarda yer osti filtratsiya jarayonini modellashtirish va sonli yechimini olish imkonini beradi.

3. Quduqlardan foydalanish orqali ekin yerlarini oqilona sug'orishni yo'lga qo'yishga yordam beradi.

4. Daryo va kanallardan yer ostiga suv sizib kirishini ta'minlash orqali yer osti suv zahirasini to'ldirish jarayonini modellashtirish imkonini beradi.

5. Zavurlar orqali yer osti suvlari sathining ko'tarilishini oldini olishni ta'minlash imkoniyatini yaratadi.

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